

Sero-Prevalence of *Leptospira hardjo* Infection among Cattle Slaughtered at Sokoto Metropolitan Abattoir, Sokoto State, North-western Nigeria

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Leptospirosis is a transmissible zoonotic disease that is widely distributed worldwide; it causes public health problems and affects both developed and developing countries. This study investigated seroprevalence of *Leptospira hardjo* infection among cattle slaughtered in Sokoto State Metropolitan Abattoir. One hundred and eighty-four (184) samples were collected aseptically from the jugular vein of different breeds of cattle (Red Bororo, Sokoto Gudali and White Fulani) at slaughter position in Sokoto metropolitan abattoir using aseptically anticoagulant-free vacutainers twice in a week and the samples were centrifuged and sera separated. Indirect Enzyme Linked-Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA) technique (specific for the detection of antibodies against *Leptospira pomona* and *L. hardjo* in bovine serum) was employed and the procedures were carried out according to the manufacturer's protocol (ELISA Bovicheck[®] Lepto HP, Bioveta, Canada). The optical density was read using an ELISA reader (Optic System IVYMEN[®] 2100C, USA). Overall prevalence of *Leptospira spp* serovar *hardjo* in the study area was found to be 17.4 % (32). The prevalence in cows was higher (18.4%) than that recorded in males (16.0%). There was absence of a statistically significant difference ($p>0.05$) in seropositivity of leptospiral infection between the bulls. The age-specific prevalence of *L. hardjo* infection showed that young cattle are more exposed but no statistical association was observed $p>0.05$. The breed specific prevalence of *Leptospira hardjo* infection showed that Sokoto Gudali recorded a higher prevalence of 28.0% (7), while White Fulani and Red Bororo and recorded a prevalence of and 16.4% (9) and 15.4% (16) respectively. There was no statistical association between breed and *Leptospiral* infection ($p>0.05$). The most predominant breed in the study area was the White Fulani cow. This study concluded that cattle in the study area are exposed to infection by *Leptospira spp*. The presence of *leptospirosis* among cattle slaughtered in the abattoir may serve as an occupational hazard to the abattoir workers. These abattoir workers are at risk of being infected by *Leptospira spp*. serovar *hardjo*. Age, sex, and breed are not associated with *Leptospira* infection in cattle slaughtered in Sokoto State abattoir.

Keywords: Abattoir, Cattle, *Leptospira hardjo*, Seroprevalence, Sokoto State

INTRODUCTION

Leptospirosis is a neglected tropical zoonotic disease of

public health importance causing significant mortalities among animals and humans (Udechukwu *et al.*, 2024). Leptospirosis is one of the most significant zoonotic bacterial diseases globally (Costa *et al.*, 2015; Bradley and Lockaby 2023), estimated to cause around 1 million

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cases and 60,000 deaths annually (Costa *et al.*, 2015). The prevalence of leptospirosis is increasing globally with a higher incidence in developing and tropical countries (Kumar, 2013). It is caused by pathogenic species of *Leptospira* a member of the *Leptospiraceae* family, order *Spirochaetales* (Fraga *et al.*, 2024). Dogs, rodents, cattle, pigs, wildlife, and other mammals that serve as unintentional hosts are the main reservoirs for this disease (Solomon *et al.*, 2012). Cattle serve as the maintenance host for *Leptospira* spp serovar *Hardjo* and *Leptospira* spp serovar *Pomona*, *Grippotyphosa*, *Icterohaemorrhagiae* and *Canicola* (Udechukwu *et al.*, 2024). *Leptospira* can be transmitted directly to humans through the handling of infected animals, making leptospirosis an occupational hazard for people that regularly handle animals, such as livestock producers, abattoirs, veterinarians, hunters and game managers, animal control workers, and scientists (Karpagam *et al.*, 2020; López-Robles *et al.*, 2021; Sykes *et al.*, 2022; Udechukwu *et al.*, 2024).

Leptospirosis in both humans and animals presents a wide range of clinical characteristics and is one of the leading causes of reproductive failure in cattle (Sridhar *et al.*, 2020). The condition is associated to reproductive issues such as dystocia, abortion, stillbirth, and infertility (Tilahun *et al.*, 2013; Robi *et al.*, 2023, Dereji *et al.*, 2024) resulting in significant financial losses. Leptospirosis has been documented in Asia, and the United States (CDC, 2000; Koizumi *et al.*, 2009). Leptospirosis in humans characterised by fever (38-40°C), rigors, Headache, retro-orbital pain, photophobia, Muscle pain localized to the calf and lumbar areas, Conjunctival suffusion, Dry cough, Nausea and vomiting, diarrhea and in severe disease manifests as icteric leptospirosis, also known as Weil disease, with the following features: Icterus or frank jaundice, Renal failure with oliguria, Hemorrhagic features, Systemic inflammatory syndrome or shock (Sandra, 2024). Leptospirosis is endemic in most areas where dengue virus is transmitted and may be mistaken for dengue, which typically is more common. Co-infection occurs in up to 8% of cases (Sandra, 2024). Leptospirosis also may co-infect with dengue and other regionally prevalent pathogens, such as malaria, hantavirus, and scrub typhus. Leptospirosis typically is a biphasic pattern of early flu-like, septicemic illness followed by an inflammatory second phase. The latter may be characterized by systemic inflammatory response syndrome (SIRS) or cytokine storm. COVID-19 may follow a similar trajectory and may complicate diagnosis in the subtropics and tropics (Sandra, 2024). These issues may complicate the diagnosis, especially in travellers or migrants presenting to non-endemic areas (Sandra, 2024). It is widely spread across Southeast Asia, Oceania, the Indian sub-continent, Latin America, and Africa, where climatic variations, flooding, inadequate sanitation, a large number of maintenance hosts (rats) and various socio-economic and cultural factors play

crucial roles in determining infection rates (Evangelista and Coburn, 2010).

Different types of rodents, wild animals, and domesticated creatures can serve as reservoirs for pathogens found in their kidney tubules, which are then expelled through their urine (Assenga *et al.*, 2015, Msemwa *et al.*, 2021). Pathogens present in an infected animal's urine can be transmitted to humans or other animals through exposure to or contact with soil, water, or vegetation where it is excreted. Individuals residing near or next to forests or jungles, as well as those working in wetlands and waterways, are also more likely to become infected with the disease (Mgode *et al.*, 2021). Studies have been conducted on cattle in Zaria, located in the Central Northern Kaduna State, showing prevalence rates ranging from 3.5% to 8.4% (Ngbede *et al.*, 2012); in Ibadan (Jagun *et al.*, 2011) and Maiduguri (Jashilagari *et al.*, 2022). Leptospirosis has been proven to occur in dogs (Agunloye *et al.*, 2002), as well as in sheep, goats, and pigs (Agunloye *et al.*, 2002; Garba *et al.*, 2013). Hence, the research sought to establish the prevalence of *Leptospira haardjo* antibodies among cattle Slaughtered in Sokoto Metropolitan Abattoir, Sokoto State, Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

This study was conducted in Sokoto metropolitan abattoir which is located at Sokoto North Local Government Area (LGA), Sokoto State. Sokoto state is geographically located at the North Western part of Nigeria between longitude 11° 30' to 13° 50' East and latitude 4° to 6° 40' North. The state shares common borders with Niger Republic to the North, Kebbi state to the South and Zamfara State to the East (National Population Commission, 2006). The State is located in the arid Sahel region, encircled by Sudanese sandy Savannah. The arid region of the country is where the state, a significant livestock producer, is located. It spans an area of approximately 32,000 square km and has a population of about 3,696,999 million people (NPC, 2006). The state has 23 Local Government Areas (Figure 1) with a majority of the population working as farmers. Due to their limited amount of farmable land and a substantial portion of the population being involved in raising animals. Sokoto benefits from its low population density, which provides ample agricultural and grazing land, contributing significantly to the state's GDP and employing approximately 70% of its workforce (NPC, 2006). Sokoto State comes in second place in the country in terms of livestock numbers, possessing 3 million cattle, 3 million sheep, 5 million goats, 4,600 camels, and a variety of poultry such as chickens, guinea fowls, ducks, and turkeys (MOCIT, 2002).

Figure 1: Map of Sokoto State showing the 23 LGA's of the State and the Study Area

Study Design

Information on the average number of animals slaughtered daily is 40-60 cattle and on the average monthly, 1,750 numbers of cattle are slaughtered. The consent to conduct the study was sorted from the Manager of Sokoto Metropolitan Abattoir. Based on the World Organization for Animal Health (OIE, 2008) recommendation, 10 % of the average number of cattle slaughtered monthly was collected monthly throughout the study period. The study population comprised of animals that were aged above one year. Information on age, sex and breed of the animal was collected and recorded on a data form.

Sample Size Determination

The sample size was estimated using the formula of Thrusfield (2010)

$$n = \frac{z^2 \times P \exp(1 - p_{exp})}{d^2}$$

n = sample size, $Z = 1.96$ (95 % Confidence Interval), P_{exp} = Expected prevalence, d =desired absolute precision.

The sample size of 51.9 minimum samples was calculated using the previous prevalence of 3.50 % by Ngbede *et al.* (2012) at a 95 % confidence interval with 5 % absolute precision. To increase the chances of detecting antigens, one hundred and eighty-four (184) samples were collected.

Sample Collection and Processing

Blood samples were collected aseptically from the jugular vein of the cattle following slaughter in aseptically sterile anticoagulant-free vacutainers twice in a week at Sokoto Metropolitan Abattoir, Sokoto State. 10 mL of blood was collected and the tubes were well labelled with a code that was specific to each cattle, and they were left in a tilted position for 2–4 hrs at room temperature to allow for clotting. The samples were then transported in an ice pack to the Central Research Laboratory of the Faculty of

Table 1: Age-specific Prevalence of *Leptospira spp serovar Hardjo* in Cattle Slaughtered in Sokoto State Metropolitan Abattoir

Age	Number Tested	Number Positive (%)
Adult	131	18(13.7)
Young	53	14 (26.4)
Total	184	32 (17.4)

$$\chi^2 = 2.85 \quad df = 1 \quad p\text{-value} = 0.092$$

Veterinary Medicine, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto State, Nigeria. Samples were kept slanted and later separated by centrifugation at 3000g for 10 minutes at room temperature. Sera was transferred into the sterile microtube (Eppendorf®) and kept at -20°C until required. Serum samples were screened for antibodies to *L. pomona* using indirect Enzyme Linked-Immunesorbent Assay (ELISA) technique kit (ELISA Bovicheck® Lepto HP) from Bioveta, Canada (specific for the detection of antibodies against *Leptospira pomona* and *L. hardjo* in bovine serum). Procedures were carried out according to the manufacturers protocol. The intensity of the colour is proportional to the quantity of antibody in the serum samples. The intensity of the colour (Optical Density) was read using an ELISA reader (Optic System IVYMEN® 2100C, USA) at 450-620nm.

Protocol

With the aid of a pipette, 100µL of positive, negative control and test samples were dispensed into the appropriate wells. These were incubated at 23°C for 30 minutes. Each well was washed three times with 300µL of 1X wash solution. The excess liquid contained in the well was removed. After the last wash, the plate was dried by tapping on an absorbent paper, after which 100µL of the diluted conjugate was dispensed into each well and incubated at 23°C for 30 minutes. The wells were rewashed as described above. Using a pipette, 100µL substrate was dispensed into each well and incubated at 23°C for 15minutes. Lastly, 100µL of stop solution was dispensed into each well. Optical density (OD) was read at 450nm not later than 15 minutes, and the result was calculated.

i. Calculation of the Ratio: For the control, the mean ODs were obtained on the plate coated with *L. Hardjo*, were calculated. The ratio for each pathogen was calculated by dividing each sample's OD for that pathogen by the positive control's mean OD for that pathogen. OD sample (*L. hardjo*) = ratio (*L. hardjo*) Mean OD positive (*L. hardjo*).

ii. Validation: The mean negative control ratio for each pathogen must be less than 0.25. The mean of positive control ODs for each pathogen must be greater than 0.75.

iii. Interpretation: A sample ratio of less than 0.20 was considered negative. A sample ratio less than 0.30 but greater or equal to 0.20 was considered suspicious and

should be retested two weeks later. A sample ratio greater than or equal to 0.30 was considered positive.

Statistical Analysis

Information from this study was entered and stored in Microsoft Excel®, where descriptive statistics were used. Data was analysed using GraphPad Prism® version 8.0.2(263). Categorical variables like age, sex and breed were evaluated using Chi-square to check for the association between variables and the percentage positive of *Leptospira*. Values of $p < 0.05$ were considered significant at 95% confidence interval.

RESULTS

Prevalence of *Leptospira* infection in Cattle from Sokoto State Abattoir in relation to age

Out of 184 sera from cattle screened for antibodies to *Leptospira spp serovar hardjo* infection using ELISA, a prevalence rate of 17.4% (32) was obtained. The age-specific prevalence of *L. hardjo* infection showed that adult cattle recorded a lower prevalence of 13.7% (18) while young cattle recorded a prevalence of 26.4% (14). However, the chi-square showed no statistical association between age and Leptospiral infection with $p < 0.05$ (Table 1).

Prevalence of *Leptospira* infection in Cattle from Sokoto State Abattoir in relation to sex

The sex-specific prevalence of *L. hardjo* infection showed that Cows recorded a higher prevalence of 18.4% (20), while bulls recorded a prevalence of 16% (12). However, the Chi-square showed no statistical association between sex and Leptospiral infection with $p < 0.05$ (Table 2).

Prevalence of *Leptospira* infection in Cattle from Sokoto State Abattoir in relation to breed

The breed-specific prevalence of *L. hardjo* infection showed that Sokoto Gudalli recorded a higher prevalence of 29.1% (16), while White Fulani and Red Bororo recorded a prevalence of 24% (6) and 23.1% (24) respectively. However, the Chi-square showed no statistical association between breed and Leptospiral infection with $p < 0.05$ (Table 3).

Table 2: Sex specific Prevalence of *Leptospira spp serovar Hardjo* in Cattle Slaughtered in Sokoto State Metropolitan Abattoir.

Sex	Number Tested	Number Positive (%)
Bulls	75	16 (12)
Cows	109	20(18.4)
Total	184	32 (17.4)

$$\chi^2 = 0.12 \quad df = 1 \quad p - \text{value} = 0.73$$

Table 3: Breed specific Prevalence of *Leptospira spp serovar Hardjo* in Cattle Slaughtered in Sokoto State Metropolitan Abattoir

Breeds	Number Tested	Number Positive (%)
Red Bororo	104	16 (15.4)
Sokoto Gudalli	25	16 (28.0)
White Fulani	55	9(16.4)
Total	184	32 (17.4)

$$\chi^2 = 1.50 \quad df = 2 \quad p\text{-value} = 0.47$$

DISCUSSION

The prevalence rate in this study is lower than the findings of Sharma *et al.* 2014 who reported (37%) in cattle and goats (29%) using MAT and bacterial culture from kidney tissues. Our findings is higher than the findings of Rebecca *et al.* (2024) who reported 18% out of 131 cattle examined; Behera *et al.* (2010) in eastern India (16%); Ngbede *et al.* (2012a) 3.5% in Zaria, Kaduna state, Nigeria and seroprevalence of *Leptospira hardjo* (4.3 %) in cattle reported by Jashilagari *et al.* (2022). The difference may result from environmental influences, different breeds, the organism specific geographical location, and the lack of leptospirosis vaccination programs in the study area.

The variations in prevalence may also be likely due to different sensitivities of the assay techniques employed or the type of samples used. This also confirm findings of Ngbede *et al.* (2013) suggesting the persistence of *Leptospira* infection among livestock and humans in Nigeria. The current research demonstrated the frequency and transmission of *Leptospira* bacteria in livestock within the research location. The study area likely has a high rate of leptospirosis due to frequent interactions between humans and potential host animals for the disease. Past research indicated that human actions like raising livestock, farming in marshy regions, fishing, or working in areas where rodents are present are important in passing on pathogens to humans (Benacer *et al.*, 2016, Mgode *et al.*, 2021). As seen in previous research, animals like goats and cattle could be reservoir hosts for leptospirosis or contract *Leptospira* serovars from other animals, such as rodents (Assenga *et al.*, 2015, Mgode *et al.*, 2021, Msemwa *et al.*, 2021).

The study's results indicated that *Leptospira spp* causes leptospirosis in the study location, aligning with Garba *et al.* (2013) findings. The occurrence rate in cows was greater (18.4%) compared to that observed in bulls (12.0%), suggesting that both genders are equally susceptible to the organism (Ngbede *et al.*, 2012). The

prevalence of *L. hardjo* infection varies by age, with young cattle having higher exposure rates than adult cattle, which concur with the findings of Agunloye *et al.* (2002). The difference in age categories could be due to either immune status or repeated exposure of the adult. Sokoto Gudali had the highest prevalence of *Leptospira hardjo* infection at 28.0%, followed by White Fulani at 16.4% and Red Bororo at 15.4%. The White Fulani was the most prevalent breed in the study region. There is a chance that these seemingly healthy animals with antibodies to *Leptospira spp. serovar Hardjo* could be spreading the infection to other animals. and humans (Ngbede *et al.*, 2012a). The exchange of *Leptospira* serovars among humans, goats, and cattle highlights the effects of interactions between people and livestock, leading to the transmission of pathogens across interaction points. Other studies have also found comparable findings on the transmission of *Leptospira* between humans and livestock (Assenga *et al.*, 2015; Mgode *et al.*, 2021).

CONCLUSION

This research demonstrated that cattle in the specific region are at risk of being infected by *Leptospira spp*, with a prevalence rate of 17.4% in slaughtered cattle. The existence of leptospirosis in cattle slaughtered at the abattoir can pose a risk to the abattoir workers. These workers are in danger of contracting *Leptospira spp. serovar Hardjo*. There is no correlation between age, gender, or type of cattle breed and *Leptospira* infection in animals slaughtered at Sokoto State Abattoir. Nevertheless, it is important for decision makers to guarantee proper sanitation in slaughterhouses and create efficient plans for controlling and preventing diseases, ultimately decreasing the effects of leptospirosis in the area and potential spread across borders.

Based on the prevalence observed in this study, it is

strongly advised to implement health interventions and educational programs to raise awareness about the transmission and prevention of leptospirosis. The thorough investigation might involve a bigger sample size for each interface and the addition of wild animals. It is recommended to use multidisciplinary analysis, which includes molecular analysis, to uncover the phylogenetic connections between hosts of serovars, because MAT (Microscopic Agglutination Test) cannot reveal the causes of overlaps and divergence immune relationships among livestock as they share few *Leptospira* serovars although they share foraging and dens.

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Ethical Approval

The research does not contain animal experimental trials. No ethical clearance obtained, but permission (consent) was obtained from the abattoir management to collect small volumes of blood samples for serological studies from the slaughtered cattle.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no competing interests regarding publication of this paper.

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REFERENCES

- Agunloye, C. A., Alabi, F.O., Odemuyiwa, S.O., Olaleye, O.D. (2002). Leptospirosis in Nigerian: A Seroepidemiological Survey. *Indian Vet. J.* 78 (5), 371–375.
- Assenga JA, Matemba LE, Muller SK, Mhamphi GG, Kazwala RR 2015 Predominant *Leptospira* serogroups circulating among humans, livestock and wildlife in Katavi-Rukwa ecosystem, Tanzania. *PLoS Negl. Trop. Dis.* 9: e0003607
- Behera, B., Rama, C., Anubhav, P., Anant, M., Lalit D., Martha, M.P., Ekta G., Shobha, B. and Parveen, A. (2010). Co-infection due to leptospira, dengue and hepatitis E: a diagnostic challenge. *Journal of Infectious diseases in Developing Countries.* 4 (1):48-50.
- Benacer D, Zain SNM, Sim SZ, Khalid NKNM, Galloway RL, Souris M and Thong KL 2016 Determination of *Leptospira borgpetersenii* serovar Javanica and *Leptospira interrogans* serovar Bataviae as the persistent *Leptospira* serovars circulating in the urban rat populations in Peninsular Malaysia. *Par. Vect.* 9: 1-11.
- Bradley EA, Lockaby G (2023) Leptospirosis and the environment: A review and future directions. *Pathogens* 2023; 2(9): 1167.
- CDC (2000). Outbreak of acute febrile illness among participants in Eco Challenge Sabah 2000–Malaysia. *Morb. Mort. Weekly Rep.* DOI: 10.1001/jama.284.13.1646-jwr1004-5-1
- Costa F, Hagan JE, Calcagno J, Kane M, Torgerson P, et al. (2015) Global morbidity and mortality of leptospirosis: a systematic review. *PLoS Negl Trop Dis* 9(9): 0003898
- Dereje, TR., Ararsa, B., Beksisa U., Melkam, A. (2024). Seroprevalence of *Coxiella burnetii*, *Leptospira interrogans* serovar hardjo, and *Brucella species* and associated reproductive disorders in cattle in southwest Ethiopia. 10 (3), 255-58.
- Evangelista, K.V. and Coburn, J. (2010). *Leptospira* as an emerging pathogen: a review of its biology, pathogenesis and host immune responses. *Future Microbiol.* 5(9), 1413-1425.
- Fraga TR, Carvalho E, Isaac L, Barbosa AS (2024). *Leptospira and leptospirosis In Molecular Medical Microbiology.* Academic Press, pp: 1849-1871.
- Garba B., O.O. Faleke, M.D. Saliyu, H.S. Garba, N. Suleiman, S. Bashir and M. Aliyu (2013). Seroprevalence of Leptospire in Sheep Slaughtered at Sokoto Metropolitan Abattoir. *Sci J Vet Adv.* 2(3) 26-29.
- Jagun A.T., Ajayi O.L., Ilugbo M.O., Olugasa B.O., Kafer J. and Schobesberger H. (2011). Isolation and Prevalence of Pathogenic *Leptospira interrogans* in Slaughtered Cattle in two Abattoirs in Southwestern Nigeria. *Tribun EU.*, 2011(1), 235–7.
- Jashilagari, S., Bura T.P., Ma'aruf, M. I., Joshua, D., Modu, M.B., Gideon, D. M. (2022). Serological Evidence of *Leptospira hardjo* Antibodies and The Incidence of Reproductive Disorders in Selected Smallholder Cattle and Goat Farms from Maiduguri, Nigeria. *J. Advanced Vet. Res.* 12 (1), 1-5.
- Karpagam, K.B.; Ganesh, B. (2020). Leptospirosis: A Neglected Tropical Zoonotic Infection of Public Health Importance—An Updated Review. *Eur. J. Clin. Microbiol. Infect. Dis.* 39(5), 835–846.
- Koizumi, N., Muto, M., Tanikawa, T., Mizutani, H., Sohmura, Y. Hayashi, E., Akao, N., Hoshino, M., Kawabata, H., Watanabe, H. (2009). Human leptospirosis cases and the prevalence of rats harbouring *Leptospira interrogans* in urban areas of Tokyo, Japan. *J. Med. Microbiol.* 58 (9), 1227-1230.
- Kumar SS (2013) Indian guidelines for the diagnosis and management of human leptospirosis. *Med Upd* 1: 24-29
- López-Robles, G.; Córdova-Robles, F.N.; Sandoval-Petris, E.; Montalvo-Corral, M. (2021). Leptospirosis at Human-Animal-Environment Interfaces in Latin-America: Drivers, Prevention, and Control Measures. *Biotechnia*, 23 (3), 89–100.
- Mgode GF, Mhamphi GG, Massawe AW and Machang'u RS 2021). *Leptospira* Seropositivity in humans, livestock and wild animals in a semi-arid area of Tanzania. *Pathogens* 10: 696.
- MOCIT (2002): Guide to Sokoto State's Economic Potentials. Commerce Department, Ministry of Commerce, *Industry and Tourism*, Sokoto State. Pp 4-18.
- Msemwa B, Mirambo MM, Silago V, Samson JM, Majid KS, Mhamphi G, Genchwere J, Mwakabumbe SS, Mngumi EB, Mgode G and Mshana SE. (2021). Existence of similar *Leptospira* serovars among dog keepers and their respective dogs in Mwanza, Tanzania, the need for a one health approach to control measures. *Pathogens.* 10(5), 609.
- Ngbede E.O., Raji M.A., Kwanashie C.N., Okolocha E.C., Momoh A.H., Adole E.B. (2012) Risk Practices and Awareness of Leptospirosis in an Abattoir in North-western Nigeria. *Sci J Vet Adv* 1(2), 65–9.
- Ngbede, E. O., Raji, M. A., Kwanashie, C. N., Okolocha, C., Maurice, N. A., Akange, E. N., and Odeh, L. E. (2012a). Leptospirosis among zebu cattle in farms in Kaduna State, Nigeria. *Asian Pacific J. Trop. Disease*, 2(5), 367-369.
- Ngbede, E.O., Raji, M.A., Kwanashie, C.N., Okolocha, E.C. (2013). Serosurvey of *Leptospira* spp serovar Hardjo in cattle from Zaria, Nigeria. *Rev. Vet. Med.* 164(2), 85-89.
- NPC (2006). *Population Census figure*, National Census Commission, Abuja, Nigeria, pp 1-40.
- Rebecca, H., Laurent, C., Jonas, E., Karine, G., Mathias, G., Audrey, C., Camille, E., Gualbert, H., Thibaut, L., Julien, C., Gauthier, D., Florence, A. (2024). Seroprevalence and renal carriage of pathogenic *Leptospira* in livestock in Cotonou, Benin. *VetMed Sci.* <https://doi.org/10.1002/vms3.1430>
- Robi, D.T., Bogale, A., Urge, B., Melkam, A. and Shiferaw, T. (2023). Neglected zoonotic bacteria causes and associated risk factors of

- cattle abortion in different agro-ecological zones of southwest Ethiopia. *Vet. Immunol. Immunopathol.* doi: 10.1016/j.vetimm. 2023.110592.
- Sandra, G.G. (2024). Leptospirosis. Available on: https://emedicine.medscape.com/article/220_563-overview?form=fpf. Retrieved on 31/10/2024, 2:09pm.
- Sharma, S., Vijaychari, P., Sugunan, A.P., Kalimuthusamy, N. (2014). Sero- prevalence and carrier status for leptospirosis in cattle and goats in Andaman Island, India. *J. Vet. Sci. Tech.* 5(5),1-4.
- Solomon D., Gift M., Lisa M., Keith D., Davis M.P. (2012). Seroprevalence of leptospirosis in dogs in urban Harare and selected rural communities in Zimbabwe. *Onderstepoort J. Vet. Res.* 79(1): 1-6.
- Sridhar, M. K., Okareh, O. T. & Mustapha, M. Assessment of knowledge, attitudes, and practices on water, sanitation, and hygiene in some selected LGAs in Kaduna State, Northwestern Nigeria. *J. Environ. Public Health.* <https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/65325> 12(2020).
- Sykes, J.E.; Haake, D.A.; Gamage, C.D.; Mills, W.Z.; Nally, J.E. (2022). A Global One Health Perspective on Leptospirosis in Humans and Animals. *J. Am. Vet. Med. Assoc.* 260(13), 1589–1596.
- Tilahun, Z., Reta, D. and Simenew, K. (2013). Global epidemiological overview of leptospirosis. *Int. J. Microbiol. Res.* 4(1):9-15.
- Udechukwu, C.C., Kudi, A.C., Abdu, P.A., Pilau, N.N., Jolayemi, K.O., Okoronkwo, M.O., and Kuyet, G.Z. (2024). Leptospirosis: A Review of the Silent Threat in West Africa. *J Vet Sci Res.*, DOI: 10.23880/oajvsr-16000275.
- World organization for Animal Health (Office International des epizooties) 2008, *Manual for standards and diagnostic test and vaccine*, chapter 2.1.9 OIE, Paris 251-264.